

HRM practices during the global recession (2008 – 2010): evidence from globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka

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Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V., & Perera, G. (2012). HRM practices during the global recession (2008-2010): Evidence from globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka. Strategic Outsourcing: An International Journal, 5 (3), 188 – 212.

This Version is available at: doi 10.1108/17538291211291747

Purpose- To investigate human resource management (HRM) practices adopted by firms during the recession period of 2008–2010 and their impact on employees' happiness at work, and whether there are any differences by the size of the firm.

Design/methodology/approach- Two survey questionnaires were developed for the study, one targeting non-managerial employees and the other targeting senior managers. Two random samples of non-managerial employees (N=263) and senior managers (N=76) attached fulltime to globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka responded. For the data analysis, descriptive statistics, factor analysis, analysis of variance, and multiple regression were used.

Findings- It was found that reduction in financial rewards, reduction in benefits, and training and development provision significantly vary by the size of the firm. Further, the communication of information, performance management, reduction in financial rewards, and reduction in benefits significantly predict employees' happiness at work during recession.

Research limitations/implications – The research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology. Respondent senior managers were reluctant to provide actual data on layoffs and quits during the recession period.

Practical implications – The findings of this study would contribute for practitioners to better understand the HRM practices adopted by the firms during recession and effects of these HRM practices on employees' level of happiness at work.

Social implications – Employees' happiness by doing what is worth doing, pursuing important goals, and using one's skills and talents during the economic recession could be affected by the HRM practices adopted during the recession.

Originality/value- It is evident that firms facing economic recession launch cost reduction initiatives such as pay cuts and freeze in new hires. From the academic and practical standpoint it is important to identify the influence of such HRM practices adopted during the recession on employees' happiness at work. However, available research does not provide sufficient understanding about the influence of HRM practices on employees' happiness at work during recession as empirical research on this area is presently lacking.

Key words: globally distributed software development, happiness at work, human resource management practices, recession.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Unprecedented events that took place in the late 2007 in the United States market for sub-prime mortgages escalated to global proportions leading to the global economic recession (International Telecommunication Union, 2009; Stefaniak et al., 2012). The literature identifies the recession that began in December 2007 as the Great Recession as it is the longest economic downturn since the Great Depression (deWolf and Klemmer, 2010; Stefaniak et al., 2012). This recession has afflicted the world's largest economic zones of the United States, Japan and the European Union as well as the economies of many other countries around the globe. This recession has far-reaching consequences due to a sharp decline in investment and massive slowdown in world trade growth compared with two other economic downturns of the Asian crisis of the late 1990s and the *dot.com* bust of 2001 - 2002 (International Telecommunication Union, 2009).

At the firm level, recession is one of the most significant exogenous shocks to a firm's viability and continued profitability (Mascarenbas and Aaker, 1989), and the prospects of survival for firms suffering through a recession are often dubious (Pearce and Michael, 2006). The present study focused on the globally distributed software development firms. To take the advantage of lower costs and broader talent pools around the world, many firms in the U.S., Europe and the Asia Pacific have located their research and development centres overseas or sending their programming, engineering, and technical back office work overseas. As a consequence, many software products, components, and custom-designed systems are created in globally distributed teams in the South Asia, China, Southeast Asia, Russia, Eastern Europe, and Latin America (Cusumano, 2008). Innovations in ICT have accelerated the growth of this sector during the last two decades (Kotlarsky et al., 2007). However, the literature also suggests that offshore outsourced software development is one of the sectors that have severely affected by this 2008-2010 recession (Latham and Braun, 2008; Rao, 2009). The literature suggests that, on the one hand, the recession had further expedited the process of cost cutting resulting in increased outsourcing by firms in developed countries (Agarwal and Nisa, 2009; International Telecommunication Union, 2009; Kraemer et al., 2010). On the other

hand, the recession had promoted the adoption of cost cutting strategies by offshore outsourcing firms in developing countries (International Telecommunication Union, 2009; Rao, 2009). Therefore, the literature suggests that recession had mixed effects on offshore outsourcing firms in the developing countries (International Telecommunication Union, 2009). For instance, the Chilean offshore software and IT services industry was expected to be severely affected by the recession in 2009, but at the same time this sector was expected to grow by 10% in 2009 (International Telecommunication Union, 2009). However, the available literature does not provide sufficient empirical evidence on how offshore outsourcing firms in developing countries reacted to economic recession that began in the late 2007. The present study investigated human resource management (HRM) practices adopted by offshore outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka during 2008 – 2010 recession.

The literature suggests the importance of HRM practices in keeping everyone calm and together through the recession (Bidya, 2009, Brundage and Koziel, 2010; Giancola, 2009; Mohrman and Worley, 2009). For instance, it is evident that firms facing economic recession launch cost reduction initiatives such as pay cuts and freeze in new hires. Yet, the literature suggests that many firms are not successful in implementing cost reduction strategies as they ignored the importance of obtaining positive emotional support of their employees for cost reduction initiatives and their commitment to behaviour change that reduces costs (Katzenbach and Bromfield, 2009). This suggests the importance of effectively managing employees' beliefs and attitudes through recession (Bidya, 2009, Brundage and Koziel, 2010; Giancola, 2009; Mohrman and Worley, 2009). In this regard, the organisational behaviour literature categorises organisational performance measures into two, namely, financial performance measures and non-financial performance measures (Foong and Yorston, 2003). According to this categorisation, employee beliefs and attitudes (such as employees' happiness, job satisfaction, and turnover intention) are identified as non-financial organisational performance measures (Foong and Yorston, 2003). In the present study, employees' happiness at work is considered as a non-financial organisational performance measure. The literature on HRM suggests that HRM practices adopted by firms predict employee beliefs and attitudes (Petrescu and

Simmons, 2008; Brown et al., 2008). The specific literature on economic recessions suggests that even though employees' happiness at work is important, employees' happiness at work could be negatively influenced by HRM practices adopted when experiencing challenging times of economic recession (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Therefore, the present study investigates whether employees' happiness at work had been influenced by HRM practices adopted during the recession period of 2008-2010. From the academic and practical standpoint it is important to identify the influence of HRM practices adopted during the recession on employees' happiness at work. However, available research does not provide sufficient understanding about the influence of HRM practices on employees' happiness at work during recession as empirical research on this area is presently lacking. Therefore, present study investigated whether HRM practices used during 2008-2010 recession influence employees' happiness at work.

Further, the literature suggests that firm size affects a firm's strategic response to environmental threats represented by economic recession (Latham, 2009; Shama, 1993). For instance, Latham (2009) provides evidence that cost and headcount reductions tend to be the preferred strategy of large firms during 2001–2003 economic downturn. However, debate continues as to whether strategic response of small and medium firms differs from the response of large firms. Therefore, we believe that empirical investigations are needed to provide sufficient evidence to help academics and practitioners for decision making. Yet, it is very rare to find previous research that investigated the effect of firm size on firms' response to recession; it is even rarer to find studies that investigated the differential effects of firm size on HRM decisions during recession.

In the above context, based on two samples of senior managers (N=76) and non-managerial professional employees (N=263) attached fulltime to globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka, the present study investigated HRM practices adopted by the firms during the recession period of 2008–2010 and their impact on employees' happiness at work, and whether there are any differences by the size of the firm (small, medium or large). It is expected that the findings of this study will provide valuable information for academics and

organizational leaders. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Literature review and hypotheses

Firm size and response to recession

The literature suggests that the manner in which firms strategically respond to environmental change would be a function of firm size. Previous studies suggest that large firms cope better with changing environmental conditions due to economies of scale, economies of scope, and learning effects (Ghemawat, 1986). Accordingly, previous studies suggest that small firms are at a competitive disadvantage when coping with changing environmental conditions due to their lack of scale to distribute fixed costs across production, limitations in product and geographic scope, and lack of development in institutional wisdom (Ghemawat, 1986). Yet, the literature suggests that small firms are more sensitive to changing market needs and possess more adaptive capabilities to enact a rapid response than their large counterparts (Latham, 2009).

During a deep and prolonged downturn, firms should introduce practices that build capability in the organization, not only to withstand the uncertainties of the rough time better, but also to emerge stronger for the future (Mohrman and Worley, 2009; Stefaniak et al., 2012). However, the understanding of how firms respond to economic recession is very limited as few empirical studies examined the response of firms of different size to recession (Latham, 2009; Shama, 1993). In one of such studies, Shama (1993) reveals that large firms focused more on cutting costs while small firms focused more on market segmentation tactics during recession. Further, Latham (2009) reveals that significant differences exist in the nature of response to 2001-2003 recession between small and large software development firms in USA, where cost and headcount reductions were central to the strategic response of large firms while revenue-generating strategies were central to the strategic response of small firms. Such previous findings imply that the firms of different size respond differently when faced with the challenges of economic recession. Yet, we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated HRM practices adopted by firms of different size during recession. In the above

context, the present study investigated HRM practices adopted by small, medium and large globally distributed software development firms in responding to environmental change and uncertainty presented over the recession period of 2008-2010.

Following the previous studies (such as Latham, 2009), we assessed firm size by the number of employees full-time attached to the organization. Based on the available industry statistics and preliminary investigations made by the authors about the industry in Sri Lanka, firms with less than 50 employees were identified as small, 51 to 200 as medium, and more than 200 as large.

HRM practices during recession

The literature suggests that HRM function plays a bigger role during tough times of recession than during the periods of prosperity and growth (Bidya, 2009). Organizations should adopt HRM practices that help them, on the one hand, to withstand the uncertainties of recession and to emerge stronger for the future (Mohrman and Worley, 2009), and on the other hand to keep everyone in the organization calm and together during the recession (Bidya, 2009). The literature identifies HRM practices that are frequently adopted during recession as the communication of information, performance management, and cost reduction strategies such as pay cuts, freeze in new hires, reduction in training budgets, and lay offs (e.g., Bidya, 2009; Lieber, 2009b ; Katzenbach and Bromfield, 2009; Mohrman and Worley, 2009; Stern, 2009).

Communication of information. The literature emphasises the importance of organizations being honest and open with their employees when faced with challenges of recession (Bidya, 2009; Mohrman and Worley, 2009; Stern, 2009). Open communication sharing business information, challenges, successes, and future direction with employees reduces the anxiety level of employees (Bidya, 2009; Lieber, 2009b; Mohrman and Worley, 2009; Stern, 2009). For instance, Lieber (2009a, p. 96) suggests that truthful, consistent communication ease the stress for departing employees and for their supervisors. Mohrman and Worley (2009) and Lieber

(2009b) suggest that communicating about how the firm is adjusting its direction in response to new realities builds trust with the remaining employees.

Although the literature reviewed earlier implies that the firms of different size respond differently when faced with challenges of an economic recession, we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated communication practices used by firms of different size during recession. Therefore, we assume that small firms will be in more advantageous position due to its limited employee numbers in communicating information to its employees than medium or large firms. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1: There will be significant differences in the level of communicating information by small, medium and large firms, where the level of communicating information by small firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

Work design and performance management. The literature suggests that a firm's work systems are challenged when faced with tough economic conditions (Bidya, 2009; Brundage and Koziel, 2010; Mohrman and Worley, 2009). According to Mohrman and Worley (2009), there is a need to alter a firm's cost structure and scale in responding to recession. For instance, layoffs may lower costs but rarely reduce the workload. Hence, there is a need to manage the firm's talent effectively by re-designing work systems (Mohrman and Worley, 2009). In this regard, Bidya (2009) states that the remaining employees are the ones who need to do more work and work longer hours with fewer resources to maximize time and cut costs. Therefore, organizational restructuring should ensure that the right talent is applied to the right tasks as employees carry out work (Mohrman and Worley, 2009).

In this regard, the literature identifies the importance of a performance management system which involves employees in setting targets, provides feedback and helps to improve employees' comfort levels, and adheres them to a timetable during recession (Bidya, 2009; Katzenbach and Bromfield, 2009; Stern, 2009). Mohrman and Worley (2009) suggest that firms could involve managers and employees to work together to set, test, and reset goals and targets drawing clear boundaries about resources and decision rights during recession while

Lieber (2009b) suggests that firms could enlist employees in solving core challenges and pinpointing opportunities during recession. In this regard, Bidya (2009) suggests the importance of involving employees in the planning process as it boosts their morale and confidence, helps to avoid any communication gaps in the process, and provides them with a clear picture of what the firm expects from them and what they need to accomplish during recession. Bidya (2009) and Brundage and Koziel (2010) emphasize the importance of ensuring employees complete assigned tasks on time and on or under budget through effective monitoring and feedback mechanisms. The literature also suggests the importance of building self-organizing capabilities of employees and allowing them to adjust their work assignments to address work priorities, which in turn improve adaptive capacity of the firm during recession (Mohrman and Worley, 2009). Therefore, as stated by Bidya (2009, p. 27) a solid performance management system could ensure that its employees not only fulfil their responsibilities, but do so to the best of their abilities and up to the organization's expectations.

Overall, the literature reviewed above implies the importance of performance management during the recession. Further, the literature reviewed earlier implies that the firms of different size respond differently when faced with challenges of an economic recession. In this regard, as we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated performance management practices adopted by firms during recession, we assume that large firms will be in more advantages position due to the possibilities of having more solid systems and processes in managing its people than small or medium sized firms. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H2: There will be significant differences in the level of performance management by small, medium and large firms, where the level of performance management by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

Training and development. The literature suggests that investment in training and development during recession serves as an important retention and reward mechanism that increases employees' commitment to the future (Mohrman and Worley, 2009; Rao, 2009). However, the

literature also suggests that many firms take measures to bring down budget allocations for training and development in economic recession perceiving that training is nonessential to their firms in such challenging financial times (Lieber, 2009b; Rao, 2009). Although reductions in the allocation of resources for training is a common approach to save costs in the short run, the literature also suggests that reductions in training investment during recession can not be justified (Bidya, 2009; Lieber, 2009b; Rao, 2009; Mohrman and Worley, 2009). For instance, Mohrman and Worley (2009) suggest that reduction in training investment, on the one hand, increases cynicism among employees, and, on the other hand, makes capability development harder and more costly when the economy is picking up. Rao (2009) states that firms in IT and IT enabled services sectors should not perceive training budget as a prime source for cost cuts, rather they should maintain if not increase their training allocation during recession. According to Rao (2009) training provision during recession provides confidence in employees to execute their tasks effectively and keeps them fully engaged rather than wasting their energy in worries about the likely consequences of recession on them and their firms. Hence, investment in training keeps employees engaged during recession and helps to upgrade and update their skills and abilities thereby enhancing their productivity.

Although the literature reviewed earlier implies that the firms of different size respond differently when faced with challenges of an economic recession, we have not come across specific previous empirical studies that investigated training and development practices adopted by firms of different size during recession. Yet, the literature reviewed earlier suggests that small firms are more sensitive to the environment due to the lack of financial resources compared with that of large firms. Hence, we assume that large firms will be in a better position in providing training and development opportunities due to their financial strength than small or medium sized firms. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H3: There will be significant differences in the level of training and development provision by small, medium and large firms, where the level of training and development provision by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

Rewards. Firms facing economic recession launch rewards reduction initiatives (Giancola, 2009; Lewis, 2009). For instance, firms offer three or four day week, which reduce employees' wage bill without reducing the workforce. In this regard, Giancola (2009) states that although firms tend to cut wages during recession, wage cuts not only reduce employees' morale and productivity, but also increase employee turnover. Further, Lewis (2009) argues that in recession bonuses are scarce, but the need to be rewarded remains. In this regard, Katzenbach and Bromfield (2009) suggest that although firms initiate rewards reduction strategies solely on a financial business case, they need to develop an emotionally appealing theme as well. That is, firms should gain the positive emotional support of employees and secure their commitment to behaviour change that reduces costs (Katzenbach and Bromfield, 2009). Further, Lewis (2009) states that in recession rewards such as promotions are scarce. Yet, there is a need to address employees' psychological state of mind, possibly by other aspirations such as better hopes for the future.

Hence, during recession, employees' rewards such as wages, salary increments, bonuses, and benefits will be reduced. Further, the literature reviewed earlier suggests that large firms may adopt more cost reduction strategies than that of small firms (e.g. Latham, 2009; Shama, 1993). Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H4: There will be significant differences in the level of reduction in financial rewards by small, medium and large firms, where the level of reduction in financial rewards by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

H5: There will be significant differences in the level of reduction in benefits by small, medium and large firms, where the level of reduction in benefits by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

Further, the literature reviewed above suggests that promotional opportunities will be scarce during recession (e.g., Lewis, 2009). However, we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated promotion practices of firms of different size during recession. We assume that due to the limited number of employees attached to small firms, they may offer

limited promotional opportunities for their employees during recession than that of the other two groups. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H6: There will be significant differences in the lack of promotional opportunities for employees by small, medium and large firms, where the lack of promotional opportunities in small firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

Layoffs and new hires. Economic recession impact on demand for labour and worker flows (deWolf and Klemmer, 2010). Job openings, which are defined as the number of openings on the last day of the reference month, reflect demand for labour. New hires and layoffs reflect worker flows (deWolf and Klemmer, 2010). New hires are defined as the additions of personnel to the payroll during the reference month (deWolf and Klemmer, 2010). The literature suggests that job openings and new hires decline during recession (Rao, 2009). For instance, Rao (2009) states that, in the context of India, two sectors that showed real signs of slowdown in hiring were IT and IT enabled services sectors.

As mentioned above, layoffs, which are defined as involuntary separations initiated by employers, also reflect worker flows (deWolf and Klemmer, 2010). The literature suggests that layoffs increase during recession (deWolf and Klemmer, 2010; Katzenbach and Bromfield, 2009; Lieber, 2009a; Rao, 2009). Yet, the literature also suggests that it is worthwhile to retain existing employees instead of laying off when considering the cost, time and difficulties involved in recruiting, selecting, hiring and orienting new employees (Brundage and Koziel, 2010; Rao, 2009).

Overall, the literature reviewed above suggests that the number of new hires will be lowered and the number of layoffs will be higher during recession. Further, the literature reviewed earlier suggests that large firms may adopt more cost and headcount reduction strategies than small firms (e.g. Latham, 2009; Shama, 1993). Hence, we assume that large firms will layoff more employees and freeze new hires than that of small or medium firms. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H7: There will be significant differences in the decline in new hires by small, medium and large firms, where the decline in new hires by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

H8: There will be significant differences in the number of layoffs by small, medium and large firms, where the number of layoffs by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups.

Happiness at work during recession

Happiness can be broadly distinguished between hedonic (i.e., experiencing pleasure) and eudaimonic happiness (i.e., living well) (Fisher, 2010; Ryan et al., 2008; Waterman et al., 2008). Hedonic happiness is referred to pleasant feelings and judgments of satisfaction and focuses on maximizing experiences of positive affect (Fisher, 2010; Ryan et al., 2008; Waterman et al., 2008). Eudaimonic happiness is referred to doing what is virtuous, morally right, true to one's self, pursuing important goals, and using one's skills and talents, regardless of how one may actually feel at any point in time (Fisher, 2010). Hence, according to Ryan et al. (2008), eudaimonic happiness is not a mental state, a positive feeling, or a cognitive appraisal of satisfaction, but rather a way of living. Yet, Ryan et al. (2008) suggest that a person who engages in meaningful endeavours, actualizes his/her human potential, and is "fully functioning" experiencing eudaimonia will also experience considerable positive affect and pleasure (hedonia).

The literature suggests that the concept of happiness is applied to workplace experiences and the majority of previous research on happiness in work organizations conceptualized most happiness constructs at the individual level (Fisher, 2010). After a comprehensive review of literature, Fisher (2010, p. 391) states that happiness at work at the individual level can be explained in terms of the work itself (e.g., engagement representing affective and cognitive involvement and enjoyment of the work itself); the job including contextual features (e.g., job satisfaction representing largely cognitive judgments about several facets of the job such as pay, co-workers, supervisor, etc.); and the organization as a

whole (e.g., affective organizational commitment). Pryce-Jones (2010a) defines happiness at work as a mindset which allows individual to maximize performance and achieve his/her potential. According to Pryce-Jones (2010a, 2010b), an individual's happiness at work consists of five components, namely, contribution, conviction, culture, commitment, and confidence. Contribution is referred to the effort employees make to be effective and provide value - contributing fully to the organization makes them happier (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Conviction is referred to employees' ability to stay motivated and remain positive and focused toward the mission of the organisation whatever the circumstances (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Culture is referred to how well employees fit within the ethos and dynamics of the workplace (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Commitment is referred to the extent to which employees are engaged with their work and doing something worthwhile (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Finally, confidence is referred to employees' level of confidence in their ability and competence to do their jobs (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Further, Pryce-Jones (2010a) suggests that these core components of happiness at work is influenced by three other attributes, namely, pride and trust that employees have in the organization and recognition employees receive from the organization for the work they do. Previous studies provide evidence that individuals' happiness in the organizational context has beneficial consequences for employees as well as organizations (Fisher, 2010; Pryce-Jones, 2010b).

In the present study, the focus is on happiness at work by doing what is worth doing, pursuing important goals, and using one's skills and talents during the economic recession. The literature emphasizes the need of happiness at work when experiencing prolonged tough and challenging times of economic recession (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). Yet, employees' happiness may decrease during recession (Pryce-Jones, 2010a, 2010b). The literature suggests that the health and well-being of individuals are severely at risk during recession due to workplace restructuring, job losses, job insecurities, pension deficits, and other financial worries (Cooper, 2009), which in turn negatively influence their happiness. For instance, Bidya (2009) suggests that downsizing and restructuring lead to layoff several employees at one time and those employees remaining in the organisation may experience low levels of happiness

due to layoffs and the associated pains of uncertainty. Bidya (2009) also suggests that remaining employees' happiness may further decreased due to overwork as they are the ones who need to do more work with fewer resources and need to work longer hours and shorter days to maximize time and cut costs (Bidya, 2009). Pryce-Jones (2010b) also reveals that less happier employees may loose their levels of self belief, confidence, resilience, motivation, goal achievement and engagement, which in turn may negatively impact on product/project delivery, new idea generation, and acceptance of, and adaptation to, change. The literature suggests that employees' happiness during recession may have adverse consequences. For instance, Pryce-Jones (2010b) provides evidence that the level of presenteeism is higher among less happier employees, where they are physically in the organistion, but mentally absent leading to more disconnectedness, delays, mistakes, misunderstandings, malicious gossip, and conflict during recession. Pryce-Jones (2010b), further, suggests that in the time of recession, pride and trust that employees have in the organization and recognition employees receive from the organization for the work they do may plummet, and in turn employees may experience low levels of happiness at work.

Based on the literature reviewed above on the happiness at work during recession, HRM practices adopted by firms during recession, and the literature reviewed above that suggests the firms of different size respond differently when faced with challenges of an economic recession, we propose for the present study that a) employees' level of happiness at work during recession may vary by the size of the firm, and b) HRM practices (discussed above) adopted during recession may differently impact on employees' levels of happiness by the size of the firm. However, we have not come across specific previous empirical studies that investigated the employees' level of happiness at work and impact of HRM practices on their happiness during recession by the firms of different size. Based on the literature reviewed earlier on HRM practices adopted by firms during recession and hypotheses proposed for any differences by the size of the firm (H1 to H8), we propose that a) happiness of employees attached to small firms will be higher than that of the other two groups, and b) the impact of

HRM practices on the employees' level of happiness at work may vary by the size of the firm.

Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H9: There will be significant differences in the employees' level of happiness at work by small, medium and large firms, where the happiness of employees attached to small firms will be higher than that of the other two groups.

H10: The impact of HRM practices on the employees' level of happiness at work may vary by the size of the firm.

Methodology

Sample

The study was carried out using a survey-based approach in the globally distributed software development sector in Sri Lanka. The target populations for the study are cross sections of employees and senior managers full-time employed in the present workplace at least from January 2007. Previous studies provide evidence that the majority of these firms have about two layers in the organizational hierarchy (i.e. senior management and technical specialists) (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Two random samples were selected for the study, namely, employees and senior level managers. The preliminary investigations made by the authors revealed that it is very rare to find formal HRM departments in these firms. The administration of HRM activities was mainly seen as line managers' job. In the study, the employees' sample is considered as the main sample, which provides data relating to HRM practices and employees' happiness during the recession. Managers' sample was used to verify the responses of employees. As detailed in the section on *measures*, two different survey questionnaires were prepared targeting each sample. Employees' sample comprised of technical specialists in job positions such as software engineer, business system analyst, and quality assurance engineer. Senior managers' sample comprised of people employed in the job positions of project manager or above. A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. Two questionnaires were developed for the study to collect data from each sample. The data were collected during the third quarter of 2011. According to the Sri Lanka Association

of Software and Service Companies (SLASSCOM) there are 65 registered organizations that supply products and services to offshore client firms. The list of firms received from SLASSCOM was not categorised by employee size. To ease the data collection, contact persons were identified from each firm. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this paper randomly selected employees and managers, who fulfil the selection criteria set for the study to participate in the survey. Further, participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. Four hundred survey questionnaires were distributed among 65 firms covering at least 5% of the employees in each firm. 263 usable responses resulted in a 66% response rate. With regard to the managers' sample, the number of senior level managers attached to these firms compared to employees is very limited due to the flat organizational hierarchy. Hundred and fifty survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 10% of the total senior level managers in each firm. A total of 76 usable responses resulted in a 51% response rate.

With regard to the demographics of the employees' sample, 77 per cent belonged to the age range of 25 to 30 years while 23 per cent belonged to the age range of 31 to 40 years. 63 per cent were male while 37 per cent were female. 43 per cent were married while 57 per cent were single. All the respondents had Bachelor's degrees; the possession of a Bachelor's degree is one of the highly sought for entry requirements for this profession in the globally distributed software development sector in Sri Lanka. The mean tenure in the IT industry was 6.93 years (SD = 2.03). The mean tenure in the present workplace was 4.87 years (SD = 2.52). As mentioned earlier, based on the available industry statistics and preliminary investigations made by the authors about the industry in Sri Lanka, firms with less than 50 employees were categorized as small, 51 to 200 as medium, and more than 200 as large. 21 per cent of the respondents were from firms with less than 50 employees (N=55), 31 per cent were from firms with 50 to 200 employees (N=81), and 48 per cent were from firms with more than 200 employees (N=126).

With regard to the demographics of the senior managers' sample, 6 per cent belonged to the age range of 25 to 30 years while 94 per cent belonged to the age range of 31 to 40 years. 76 per cent were male while 24 per cent were female. 88 per cent were married while 12 per cent were single. All the respondents had Bachelor's degrees. The mean tenure in the IT industry was 10.46 years (SD = 2.11). The mean tenure in the present workplace was 8.92 years (SD = 3.75). 20 per cent of the respondents were from firms with less than 50 employees (N=15), 32 per cent were from firms with 50 to 200 employees (N=24), and 48 per cent were from firms with more than 200 employees (N=37).

Information regarding population characteristics of employees in the globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka is difficult to be found. When the sample characteristics are compared with IT workforce statistics of the country, at the end of 2006 offshore IT outsourcing sector had approximately a 30,000 member IT workforce. They are employed by three employer groups, namely, IT sector (also known as IT suppliers, such as globally distributed software development), non-IT Sector (also known as ICT users, such as commercial banks) and the Government. Of these 30,000 total IT workforce, IT sector has approximately a 13,000 members and the majority of them are employed in firms that supply products and services to offshore client firms (SLICTA, 2007).

Measures

All constructs were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). Cronbach's α of each scale was examined and principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's α values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2006).

Of the two questionnaires, the employees' questionnaire is considered as the main data collection instrument. It consisted of 19 questions relating to HRM practices (communication, performance management, training and development, financial rewards, benefits, and promotional opportunities) and employees' happiness during the recession. Managers' questionnaire was used to verify the responses of employees and it consisted of 14 questions relating to HRM practices. Data relating to new hires and layoffs were collected only from managers. Reliability and validity statistics for all multi-item constructs of HRM practices (employees' questionnaire data) are shown in Table 1. Measures used are as follows.

Take in Table 1

Performance management. Employees' views on the level of performance management during the recession were measured by six items (refer to Table 1). Managers' views on the level of employees' performance management during the recession were also measured by the same six items mentioned above. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where Cronbach's $\alpha = .723$, Eigenvalue = 1.251, and explained variation = 67.08 per cent (results are not shown in a Table).

Reduction in financial rewards. Employees' views on any reduction in financial rewards during the recession were measured by the two items "There was a reduction in salary increments during the recession" and "There was a reduction in bonus payments during the recession" (refer to Table 1). Managers' views on any reduction in financial rewards given for employees during the recession were measured by the item "There was a reduction in financial rewards for employees during the recession".

Reduction in benefits. Employees' views on any reduction in benefits during the recession were measured by four items (refer to Table 1). Managers' views on any reduction in benefits

given for employees during the recession were measured by the item “There was a reduction in benefits for employees during the recession”.

Communication of information. Employees’ views on the level of communicating information during the recession were measured by the item “My organisation held meetings to explain the situation during the recession”. Managers’ views on the level of communicating information during the recession were measured by the item “Meetings were held to explain the situation to employees during the recession”.

Training and development provision. Employees’ views on training and development provision during the recession were measured by the item “Training was provided consistently during the recession”. Managers’ views on training and development provision for employees during the recession were measured by the item “Training was provided to employees consistently during the recession”.

Lack of promotional opportunities. Employees’ views on the lack of promotional opportunities during the recession were measured by the item “There was a decline in promotional opportunities during the recession”. Managers’ views on the lack of promotional opportunities for employees during the recession were measured by the item “There was a decline in promotional opportunities for employees during the recession”.

Decline in new hires. Managers’ views on any decline in new hires were measured by the item “There was a decline in new hires during the recession”.

Layoffs. Our preliminary investigation led to suggest that managers are reluctant to provide the actual number of layoffs during the recession. Therefore, managers’ views on any employee layoffs were measured by the item “There were employee layoffs during the recession”. In addition, managers’ responded to a question on categorical scale revealing the number of

layoffs during the recession allowing us another means of comparison across the firms of different size.

Level of happiness at work. Employees' level of happiness at work during the recession was measured by four items. The items used and results of factor analysis are shown in Table 2.

Take in Table 2

The literature suggests that individuals' perceptions may vary by their demographic characteristics, such as age. Therefore, four individual demographic characteristics (age, gender, marital status, and the total years of work experience) were controlled in the analysis. Gender was coded as female = 0, male = 1; age was coded as between 25 to 30 = 0, 31 to 40 = 1, marital status was coded as single = 0, married = 1. Work experience was measured in years.

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaires were in the English language. The items were pre-tested on a convenience sample of employees and managers that fitted with the intended samples of the study and revised accordingly.

With regard to the methods of data analysis, first, explanatory power of firm size was examined and found to be satisfactory (R^2 Adj. = .287, $p = .002$). Thereafter, ANOVA was performed to test whether there are any significant differences across the firms of different size (H1 to H9). One of the objectives of the study was to investigate the extent to which HRM practices predict happiness at work (H10). The type of data collected for independent and dependent variables (i.e., five-point Likert scale) allowed us to use multiple regression to analyse the extent to which HRM practices predict happiness at work.

Results and discussion

HRM practices during the recession

Table 3 shows types of information communicated to employees relating to recession. Table 4 shows methods used to communicate recession related information to employees.

Take in Table 3

Take in Table 4

Table 5 shows responses of employees and managers on the extent to which recession related information is communicated to the employees along with the results of ANOVA showing any differences in the level of communicating information by the size of the firm. As can be seen from Table 5, there are no significant differences by the size of the firm. Although it was hypothesized in H1 that small firms will be in more advantages position due to its less employee numbers in communicating information to its employees than medium or large firms, H1 is not supported by the data.

Take in Table 5

Table 5 also shows the extent to which performance management, the provision of training and development, reduction in financial rewards, reduction in benefits, and the lack of promotional opportunities prevailed in the firms along with the results of ANOVA depicting any differences in these by the size of the firm.

It was predicted in H2 that large firms will be managing employee performance better than small and medium sized firms. However, the results shown in Table 5 reveal that there are no significant differences by the size of the firm. Therefore, H2 is not supported by the data.

It was predicted in H3 that training and development provision by large firms will be significantly higher than small or medium sized firms. As predicted, the results shown in Table 5 reveal that there are significant differences by the size of the firm. The analysis of least significant differences (LSD) revealed that large firms are more likely to provide training and

development opportunities for employees during the recession than that of small and medium sized firms. Therefore, H3 is supported by the data.

It was predicted in H4 that reduction in financial rewards by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups. The results shown in Table 5 reveal that there are significant differences by the size of the firm. The results of LSD suggest that both small and medium firms are more likely to reduce financial rewards given for employees during the recession than large firms. Therefore, H4 is partially supported by the data.

It was predicted in H5 that reduction in benefits by large firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups. The results shown in Table 5 reveal that there are significant differences by the size of the firm. The analysis of LSD for employees' responses revealed that small and medium firms are more likely to reduce benefits during the recession than large firms. However, the managers' responses revealed that small firms are more likely to reduce benefits than large and medium sized firms. Overall, H5 is partially supported by the data.

It was predicted in H6 that the lack of promotional opportunities will be highly prevailed in small firms than the other two groups. However, the results shown in Table 5 reveal that there are no significant differences by the size of the firm. Therefore, H6 is not supported by the data.

With regard to decline in new hires, it was predicted in H7 that small firms will be more sensitive to the recession environment due to the lack of financial resources, and therefore, decline in new hires in small firms will be significantly higher than that of the other two groups. However, the results shown in Table 6 reveal that there are no significant differences by the size of the firm. Therefore, H7 is not supported by the data.

Take in Table 6

It was predicted in H8 that the number of layoffs by large firms will be significantly lower than that of the other two groups. However, the results shown in Table 6 reveal that there are no significant differences by the size of the firm. Therefore, H8 is not supported by the data.

Table 7 shows cross tabulation for the categorical scale question on the number of layoffs. The results of Pearson Chi-Square test ($X^2 = 4.58, p = .332$) also supported the results of ANOVA shown in Table 6 that there are no significant differences by the size of the firm.

Take in Table 7

Happiness at work during the recession

Table 8 shows the level of employees' happiness at work during the recession along with the results of ANOVA depicting any differences by the size of the firm. It was predicted in H9 that employees' happiness at work will vary by the size of the firm, where employees attached to large firms will experience a higher level of happiness than that of the other two groups. However, the results shown in Table 8 reveal that there are no significant differences by the size of the firm. Therefore, H9 is not supported by the data.

Take in Table 8

It was predicted in H10 that the impact of HRM practices on the level of happiness may vary by the size of the firm. The results of correlation analysis of the responses of employees are shown in Table 9 (for the total sample). Three regression analyses were conducted to identify HRM practices that significantly predict happiness at work during the recession in small, medium and large scale firms, separately. The results are shown in Table 10. The communication of information, performance management, and the provision of training and development positively predict happiness at work while reduction in financial rewards, reduction in benefits and lack of promotional opportunities negatively predict happiness at work during the recession. The HRM practices that significantly predict happiness at work of employees irrespective of the size of the firm are the communication of information, performance management, reduction in financial rewards, and reduction in benefits. Therefore, there are no

variations in the HRM practices that predict happiness at work by the size of the firm; H10 is not supported by the data.

Take in Table 9

Take in Table 10

Table 11 summarizes the results of hypotheses tests.

Take in Table 11

Conclusions and implications

The main intention of the study was to investigate HRM practices adopted by the firms during the recession period of 2008–2010 and their impact on employees' happiness at work, and whether there are any differences by the size of the firm (small, medium or large). For the study, two random samples of technical-level employees and senior-level managers engaged full-time in globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka responded. Although the literature emphasizes the importance of better understanding HRM practices effective in managing employees through recession for academics and practitioners alike, the literature provides little empirical evidence. The novel character of this research is that it investigated differential effects of firm size in adopting HRM practices during recession, which is not given due attention in the literature so far.

With regard to HRM practices adopted during the recession, senior managers' responses on HRM practices adopted in managing employees as well as non-managerial employees' experiences of HRM practices adopted in managing them were collected and analyzed separately in the study. Both managers' responses and employees' responses revealed that corporate information was communicated to employees and sound employee performance

management systems were in place. Further, there were no significant differences in communicating information and performance management across firms of different size.

With regard to cost reduction strategies adopted by firms during recession, both managers' responses and employees' responses revealed that firms reduce training and development provision during recession and large firms are more likely to provide training and development opportunities for employees during the recession than that of small and medium sized firms. Further, firms reduce financial rewards and benefits during recession, and small and medium sized firms are more likely to reduce financial rewards and benefits than that of large firms.

Other cost reduction strategies adopted by the firms, such as decline in new hires and layoffs, were inquired only from senior managers. Their responses revealed that there were decline in promotional opportunities and new hires and there was an increase in layoffs during the recession. The analysis of data further revealed that there are no significant differences in these three practices across the firms of different size.

With regard to employees' happiness at work during the recession, it was found that employees' happiness by doing what is worth doing, pursuing important goals, and using one's skills and talents during the economic recession was not at very low levels, and it does not vary by the size of the firm. Although the literature suggests that individuals' subjective experiences of happiness associated with doing what is worth doing and actualizing one's human potentials may play a critical function with respect to economic and social policies (Ryan et al., 2008), the literature also suggests that happiness in the workplace, especially in a period of recession, has not been studied to any great degree (Pryce-Jones, 2010b).

One of the main objectives of the study was to investigate HRM practices that impact on employees' happiness at work, it was found that the communication of information, performance management, reduction in financial rewards, and reduction in benefits significantly predict employees' happiness at work during recession. Interestingly, the provision of training and development opportunities and the lack of promotional opportunities do not significantly predict happiness at work. This situation can be explained based on the findings of previous

research conducted in the context of software outsourced industry in Sri Lanka. For instance, Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2010) found that hierarchical career plateau does not make a significant contribution to the career satisfaction and employees have recognised that the hierarchical plateauing is an inevitable part of their organizational life. Previous research also provides evidence that training and development activities provided by offshore IT firms emphasise short-term productivity (Mahahettige, 2008). Furthermore, Sanjeewani (2009) provides evidence that the work of offshore IT firms is organised around projects and this work environment facilitates meeting the organisation's needs for flexibility and employees' need for broad-based career experiences.

The findings also revealed that HRM practices that predict happiness at work do not vary by the size of the firm. Happiness of work during the recession is significantly predicted by the four practices of the communication of information, performance management, reduction in financial rewards, and reduction in benefits irrespective of the size of the firm.

The findings have implications for both theory and practice. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, there is surprisingly little previous empirical research that investigated employees' level of happiness during the recession, HRM practices adopted during the recession, and the effect of firm size on strategic decisions regarding HRM practices during recession. For instance, Giancola (2009) states that what the theories tend to lack are any surveys of how firms reacted to the recession. Giancola (2009) further states that "a wide overview and deep investigations are needed for leaders to put into practice all the suggestions that are put their way and steer a path through the wild oceans of a global recession". Further, the literature emphasises the importance of investigating how the firms of different size respond to economic recession as debate continues as to whether strategic response of small and medium firms differs from the response of large firms, and a small number of scholarly research investigated this area (e.g. Latham, 2009). Therefore, the findings of our study make a contribution to the literature by providing one of the few investigations on the adoption of HRM practices by firms of different size during economic recession. However, a considerable future research is needed to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results

presented in this article. Yet, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, first, the specific literature on economic recession suggests that how firms can manage through recession remains one of the most important but overlooked areas in management research (Latham and Braun, 2008). Yet, practitioners need objective data to make decisions regarding effectively managing workforce through recession. This becomes important as managers are most often untrained in how to manage employees through economic recession and they require data to make strategic decisions on multiple strategies available in responding to recession. Therefore, the findings of this study would contribute for practitioners to better understand the HRM practices adopted by the firms during recession and effects of these HRM practices on employees' level of happiness at work.

Second, with regard to specific HRM practices, the findings imply that firms tend to reduce training and development investment when faced with challenges of economic recession. Although one could argue that IT professionals today have a much shorter cycle before their skills become obsolete, the literature reviewed earlier such as Brundage and Koziel (2010) and Rao (2009) suggest the importance of making continuous investments on training as training activities may keep employees engaged during recession. Further, the findings imply the importance of establishing a performance management system that could set expectations, improve self-organizing capabilities, collaboration and creativity among employees, and provide continuous feedback. The findings also provided evidence that effective performance management during recession significantly predicts happiness at work. Furthermore, findings provide empirical support for the importance of communicating information about the firm, competitors, industry as a whole, and department/unit/team to employees, which in turn significantly predicts happiness at work during recession. In addition, the findings imply that the reduction in financial rewards and benefits significantly predict happiness at work during recession. In this regard, the literature also suggests that financial rewards of all kinds may become limited during recession (e.g. Mohrman and Worley, 2009). Yet, rewarding employees

ensures that employee performance as well as employee moral is maintained through out recession (Lieber, 2009a; Mohrman and Worley, 2009). Hence, firms that compelled to reduce or eliminate salary increases and bonuses need to focus on alternative sources of reward, such as organization wide recognition.

Third, the findings provided empirical evidence that happiness at work could be affected by the HRM practices adopted during the recession. The literature suggests the importance of happiness that comes from doing what is worth doing during the recession (Pryce-Jones, 2010b). Further, Ryan et al. (2008) suggest that individuals who are pursuing worthwhile goals and being mindfully self-regulated would likely be more socially responsible, and more prone towards social interests, and less likely to over-consume, and thus were more likely to foster a sustainable environment. Hence, organizations should ensure the happiness of employees at work. In this regard, the findings imply the HRM practices that enhance happiness at work during recession.

Fourth, the findings provide insight for organizational leaders on how HRM practices adopted through out the recession could vary by the size of the firm, i.e., small, medium and large firms. The findings imply that firms responses to recession by reducing new hires and increasing layoffs do not vary by the size of the firm while firms responses to recession by reducing financial rewards and benefits, and training and development provision vary by the size of the firm. In addition, the findings imply that the communication of information and performance management do not vary by the size of the firm (refer to Table 13). Overall, the findings imply that in adopting certain HRM practices, small and medium sized firms' response differ from the response of large firms. Hence, the findings may provide valuable insight to policy makers. However, additional research is required to better understand responses of firms of different size to economic recession.

Limitations and future research

The research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology.

Although data were collected from two separate samples of senior managers and employees,

the study relied on self-reported data. The recession period of 2008 to 2010 was considered for the study and data were collected during the third quarter of 2011. Hence, respondents comprised of firms and employees that survived the economic recession. In this regard, Latham (2009) suggests that an investigation of firms that survived the recession, especially in the technology based sectors, offers a rough measure of firm performance by means of survivability. Further, respondent senior managers were reluctant to provide actual data on HRM practices during the recession period. If data were collected from employees (existing and survived) views on layoffs of their colleagues, the influence of these on existing (survived) employees' happiness at work could have been studied. Future research could investigate an extended and detailed list of HRM practices adopted during recession. Further, future research could investigate whether there are any differences in HRM practices across different industrial sectors. Furthermore, future research could compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data to validate the links proposed in this study. In such studies, questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

References

- Agarwal, R. and Nisa, S. (2009), "Knowledge process outsourcing: India's emergence as a global leader", *Asian Social Science*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 82-92.
- Bidya, D. (2009), "A study on performance management through recession metrics during downturn", *Advances in Management*, Vol. 2 No. 10, pp. 27-30.
- Brown, A., Forde, C., Spencer, D. and Charlwood, A. (2008), "Changes in HRM and job satisfaction, 1998–2004: evidence from the Workplace Employment Relations Survey", *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 18: pp. 237–256.
- Brundage, H. and Koziel, M. (2010), "Retaining top talent still a requirement for firms", *Journal of Accountancy*, Vol. 209 No. 5, pp. 38-44.

- Cooper, C.L. (2009), "Editorial: Stress and the global recession", *Stress and Health*, Vol. 25, 127.
- Cusumano, M.A. (2008), "Managing software development in globally distributed teams", *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 51 No. 2, pp. 15-17.
- deWolf, M. and Klemmer, K. (2010), "Job openings, hires, and separations fall during the recession", *Monthly Labor Review*, May, pp. 36-44.
- Fisher, C.D. (2010), "Happiness at Work". *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 12, pp. 384-412.
- Foong, K. and Yorston, R. (2003), *Human Capital Measurement and Reporting: A British Perspective*. Retrieved from <http://www.berr.gov.uk/files/file38840.pdf> on 16th May 2012.
- Ghemawat. P. (1986), "Sustainable Advantage". *Harvard Business Review*, M: 53-58.
- Giancola, F.L. (2009), "Wage rigidity during recession", *Compensation and Benefits Review*, Vol. 41 No. 5, pp. 27-34.
- Hair, J.F. Jr, Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E. and Tatham, R.L. (2006), *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 6th ed., Pearson Education, India.
- International Telecommunication Union (2009), *Confronting the Crisis: Its Impact on the ICT Industry*. International Telecommunication Union, Geneva, Switzerland. Retrieved from: http://www.itu.int/osg/csd/emerging_trends/crisis/report-low-res.pdf
- Katzenbach, J. and Bromfield, P. (2009), "How to cut costs in a recession – with help from employees", *Strategy & Leadership*, Vol. 37 No. 3, pp. 9-16.
- Kotlarsky, J., Oshri, I., Kumar, K. and Van Hillegersberg, J. (2007), "Globally distributed component-based software development: an exploratory study of knowledge management and work division", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 161-173.
- Kraemer, K.L., Dedrick, J. and Dunkle, D. (2010), "Offshoring of software development: patterns and recession effects", Working paper, Recent Work, Personal Computing Industry Center, UC Irvine. Retrived on 18th June 2012, <http://escholarship.org/uc/item/22r9q7wp>.
- Latham, S. (2009), "Contrasting strategic response to economic recession in start-up versus established software firms", *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 47 No. 2, pp. 180-201.
- Latham, S.F. and Braun, M.R. (2008), "The performance implications of financial slack during economic recession and recovery: observations from the software industry (2001-2003)", *Journal of Managerial Issues*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 30-35.
- Lewis, S. (2009), "Leading through the credit crunch". *Industrial and Commercial Training*, Vol. 41 No. 7, pp. 363-367.

Lieber, L.D. (2009a), "How to manage terminations and layoffs in a recession", *Employment Relations Today*, Spring, pp. 95 -101.

Lieber, L.D. (2009b), "Why training dollars should remain in HR's recession budgets", *Employment Relations Today*, Fall, pp. 115-120.

Mahahettige, D.P. (2008), "Measurement and reporting of human capital in IT organisations in Sri Lanka", unpublished MBA dissertation, Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Moratuwa.

Mascarenhas, B. and Aaker, D. (1989), "Strategy over the business cycle", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 10 No. 3, pp. 199-210.

Mohrman, S.A. and Worley, C.G. (2009), "Dealing with rough times: a capabilities development approach to surviving and thriving", *Human Resource Management*, Vol. 48 No. 3, pp. 433-445.

Pearce, J. and Michael, S. (2006), "Strategies to prevent economic recessions from causing business failure", *Business Horizons*, Vol. 49, pp. 201-209.

Petrescu, A.L. and Simmons, R. (2008), "Human resource management practices and workers' job satisfaction", *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. 29 No. 7, pp. 651 – 667.

Pryce-Jones, J. (2010a), *Happiness at Work: Maximizing your Psychological Capital for Success*, United Kingdom, Wiley-Blackwell.

Pryce-Jones, J. (2010b), "Has the recession made us less happy at work?", *Manager: British Journal of Administrative Management*, Winter, pp. 26-27.

Rao, M.S. (2009), "Is cutting development and training in a recession a good idea? looking at the IT and ITeS sector in India", *Development and Learning in Organizations*, Vol. 23 No. 5, pp. 7-9.

Ryan, R.M., Huta, V. and Deci, E.L. (2008), "Living well: a self-determination theory perspective on eudaimonia", *Journal of Happiness Studies*, Vol. 9, pp. 139–170.

Sanjeevani, K.L.S. (2009), "Human resource management practices in software development organisations in Sri Lanka", unpublished MBA dissertation, Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Moratuwa.

Shama, A. (1993), "Marketing strategies during recession: a comparison of small and large firms", *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 31 No. 3, Vol. 62–72.

SLICTA (2007), *Rising Demand: The Increasing Demand for IT Workers Spells a Challenging Opportunity for the IT Industry-National IT Workforce Survey*, Sri Lanka ICT Association, Colombo.

Stefaniak, J., Baaki, J. and Blake, A.M. (2012), "An examination of the decision-making process used by organizational leaders during the great recession", *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, Vol. 24 No. 4, pp. 81-102.

Stern, S. (2009), "How to be a good boss in bad times", *Management Today*, September, pp. 38-41.

Waterman, A.S., Schwartz, S.J. and Conti, R. (2008), "The implications of two conceptions of happiness (hedonic enjoyment and eudaimonia) for the understanding of intrinsic motivation", *Journal of Happiness Studies*, Vol. 9, pp. 41-79.

Wickramasinghe, V. (2009), "Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 413-431.

Wickramasinghe, V. and Jayaweera, M. (2010), "Impact of career plateau and supervisory support on career satisfaction: a study in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka", *Career Development International*, Vol. 15 No. 6, pp. 544-561.

Tables

Table 1. HRM practices during recession - factor analysis for multi-item measures

	Factor loading		
	F1: Performance management	F2: Reduction in benefits	F3: Reduction in financial rewards
Employees were involved the in performance planning process	.787		
Continuous performance feedback was given to employees	.771		
Annual performance reviews were conducted during the recession	.763		
Employees were given due recognition to increase their performance	.723		
Employees were provided with constructive feedback to improve performance	.712		
Performance evaluation process led to strengthen the weak areas of performance	.686		
Recreational facilities were reduced during the recession		.864	
Meal facilities were reduced during the recession		.814	
Organization sponsored insurance facilities were reduced during the recession		.794	
Health facilities were reduced during the recession		.778	
There was a reduction in salary increments during the recession			.891
There was a reduction in bonus payments during the recession			.803
Eigenvalue	3.393	2.678	1.563
Explained variation	28.275	22.313	13.025
Cronbach's α	.809	.830	.757

Table 2. Factor analysis - happiness during recession

	Factor loading
I remained fully focused toward official work assignments during the recession	.882
I remained fully engaged with official work assignments during recession	.846
I contributed fully in performing job tasks during the recession	.838
I used my capabilities fully in performing job tasks during the recession	.809
Eigenvalue	2.85
Explained variation	71.29
Cronbach's α	.866

Table 3. Types of information communicated during the recession

About the organisaton	74.8%
About competitors	24.8%
About global IT industry	52.6%
About IT industry in Sri Lanka	35.9%
About the department/unit	18.5%
About the team work assigned	34.8%

Note: Percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple answers

Table 4. Communication modes used

Face-to-face	91.9%
Telephone	89.3%
Fax	16.6%
E-mails	98.5%
Printed letters	12.6%
Video conferencing	63.3%

Note: Percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple answers

Table 5. HRM practices by the size of the firm

	Employees' responses					Managers' responses				
	Small Mean (S.D.)	Medium Mean (S.D.)	Large Mean (S.D.)	F	P value	Small Mean (S.D.)	Medium Mean (S.D.)	Large Mean (S.D.)	F	P value
Communication of information	3.50 (.93)	3.19 (.88)	3.25 (.94)	1.88	.154	3.68 (.47)	3.38 (.57)	3.20 (.82)	2.81	.066
Performance management	3.01 (.85)	3.17 (.86)	3.22 (.53)	1.45	.236	3.48 (.31)	3.60 (.41)	3.69 (.49)	1.27	.285
Provision of training and development	2.75 (1.05)	2.93 (1.11)	3.30 (.80)	5.87	.003	3.46 (.46)	3.50 (.36)	4.20 (.46)	26.74	.000
Reduction in financial rewards	3.97 (1.07)	4.03 (.76)	3.45 (.89)	9.30	.000	3.31 (.47)	3.10 (.57)	2.86 (.71)	3.15	.038
Reduction in benefits	2.53 (.91)	2.67 (.62)	2.28 (.89)	6.03	.003	3.37 (.95)	1.82 (.69)	2.04 (.71)	24.51	.000
Lack of promotional opportunities	3.10 (1.01)	3.38 (.99)	3.58 (.88)	1.88	.347	2.38 (.71)	2.13 (.61)	2.25 (.70)	1.65	.521

Table 6. Decline in new hires and layoffs by the size of the firm

	Small Mean (S.D.)	Medium Mean (S.D.)	Large Mean (S.D.)	F	P value
Decline in new hires	3.93 (.68)	3.70 (.69)	3.62 (.95)	.81	.450
Layoffs	2.86 (.88)	2.87 (.74)	2.62 (.97)	2.56	.063

Table 7. Number of layoffs - results of cross tabulation

Number of layoffs	Size			Total
	<5	0 -200	> 200	
< 5	9	19	30	58
5 -10	6	5	5	16
> 11	0	0	2	2
Total	15	24	37	76

Pearson Chi-Square $X^2 = 4.58$, $p = .332$

Note: Frequencies are reported.

Table 8. Employees' happiness at work during the recession by the size of the firm

	Small Mean (S.D.)	Medium Mean (S.D.)	Large Mean (S.D.)	F	P value
Happiness at work	3.75 (.69)	3.78 (.53)	3.63 (.69)	1.60	.203

Table 9. Correlations[†]

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Age	.19	.45	1										
2 Marital status	.52	.56	.132*	1									
3 Gender	.60	.41	-.046	-.057	1								
4 Tenure	4.53	2.46	.153*	.270**	.118	1							
5 Firm size	2.33	.77	.162*	.238**	.134*	.376**	1						
6 Communication of Information	3.87	.92	.106	.124*	.079	-.122*	.078	1					
7 Performance management	3.96	.70	.039	.026	.036	.041	.099	.374**	1				
8 Provision of training and development	2.90	.98	-.077	-.006	-.098	.192**	.202**	.346**	.233**	1			
9 Reduction in financial rewards	3.92	.91	-.128	.074	.023	.287**	.159**	.198	.283**	.265**	1		
10 Reduction in benefits	3.84	.84	-.186	-.187**	.011	-.041	.153*	.166**	.057	.011	.030	1	
11 Lack of promotional opportunities	3.10	.95	-.180**	-.243**	-.050	-.006	.061	.178**	.103	.069	.301**	.349**	1
12 Happiness at work	3.43	.65	-.057	-.055	-.067	-.078	-.090	.376**	.394**	.208**	-.364	-.395**	-.151*

Notes: [†]Employees' responses (N=263). **significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 10. Regression results

Step	Variable	Small						Medium						Large					
		β	R ²	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			β	R ²	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			β	R ²	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics		
				R ²	F	Sig. of F				R ²	F	Sig. of F				R ²	F	Sig. of F	
1	Age	-.031	.065	.038	.065	.461	.884	-.124	.039	.028	.039	.373	.827	-.010	.023	.017	.017	.574	.682
	Marital status	-.084						-.093						-.021					
	Gender	-.028						-.011						-.035					
	Tenure	-.119						-.030						-.131					
2	Age	-.111	.728	.698***	.663	26.44	.000	-.127	.584	.480**	.545	7.481	.007	-.022	.392	.335**	.375	2.773	.009
	Marital status	-.026						-.094						-.020					
	Gender	-.104						-.087						-.070					
	Tenure	-.153						-.189						-.125					
	Communication of Information	.342***						.327***						.286**					
	Performance management	.391**						.239**						.284**					
	Provision of training and development	.123						.190						.165					
	Reduction in financial rewards	-.678***						-.375**						-.254*					
	Reduction in benefits	-.780***						-.393**						-.183*					
	Lack of promotional opportunities	-.118						-.181						-.172					

Note: * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

Table 11. Summary of results – happiness at work and HRM practices adopted during the recession

HRM practice	Differences in HRM practices by the size of the firm (ANOVA)	H10 - HRM practices that predict happiness at work (regression analyses) [†]		
		Small	Medium	large
Communication of information	H1 - NS	•	•	•
Performance management	H2 - NS	•	•	•
Provision of training and development	H3 - Large firms provide more than other two groups	NS	NS	NS
Reduction in financial rewards	H4 - Small and medium firms reduce financial rewards more than large firms	•	•	•
Reduction in benefits	H5 - Small and medium firms reduce benefits than large firms	•	•	•
Lack of promotional opportunities	H6 - NS	NS	NS	NS
Decline in new hires	H7 - NS [◊]			
Layoffs	H8 - NS [◊]			
Happiness at work during recession	H9 - NS [‡]			

Note: “•” indicates statistically significant coefficient estimate in regression in predicting happiness at work during the recession.

NS = Differences are not significant, [◊]Data collected only from senior managers, [‡]Data collected only from employees, [†]Results are based only on employees' responses